

Barcode ship BC05, Oslo

by
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In the interest of access to data and to enable researchers to utilise this material in the future, all measurements are submitted to the Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology (DCCD, www.dendrochronology.eu).

A total of 17 samples from the shipwreck Barcode 5 (BC05) found during excavation in Oslo, Norway were submitted for analysis. Eleven of the samples are of *Quercus sp.*, oak, one is *Pinus sp.*, pine and finally one is *Picea sp.*, spruce. Thirteen samples are dated (see fig. 1).

Just one of the dated oak samples has sapwood preserved. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that was used to make this plank is estimated to **AD 1602-16**.

Fig. 1. Diagram showing the chronological position of the tree-ring curves from the timbers from BC05.

The majority of the samples achieve a high internal correlation, forming a homogeneous group (table 1) and these are averaged to form a mean curve (Z089M001) of 183 years. This mean curve matches best with material from Southern Scandinavia (table 2), particularly with tree-ring data that is taken to come from southwest Sweden. Note the high correlation ($t = 9.85$) with another ship from the excavations at Barcode BC14 (table 2).

	Z0890089	Z089012a	Z089004b	Z089014a	Z089003a	Z089005b	Z072001a	Z089002d	Z0890019	Z089009a	Z089013a	Z089006b	Z089010a	
Z0890089	*	4,08	\	\	-	-	-	\	-	\	-	-	3,88	
Z089012a	4,08	*	-	-	-	-	3,79	-	3,1	-	-	-	-	
Z089004b	\	-	*	-	-	4,01	-	\	-	\	-	4,22	-	
Z089014a	\	-	-	*	-	4,22	-	\	\	\	\	3,24	-	
Mean curve Z089M001	Z089003a	-	-	-	-	*	-	3,82	6,01	5,34	3,66	6,82	5,97	4,5
	Z089005b	-	-	4,01	4,22	-	*	5,83	5,42	5,5	5,56	6,85	4,92	6,49
	Z072001a	-	3,79	-	-	3,82	5,83	*	4,34	4,59	4,8	4,15	4,23	6,91
	Z089002d	-	-	\	\	6,01	5,42	4,34	*	7	5,46	7,66	6,99	6,5
	Z0890019	\	3,1	-	\	5,34	5,5	4,59	7	*	7,24	8,08	8,04	5,88
	Z089009a	-	-	\	\	3,66	5,56	4,8	5,46	7,24	*	12,1	4,31	6,08
	Z089013a	\	-	-	\	6,82	6,85	4,15	7,66	8,08	12,1	*	7,97	4,56
	Z089006b	-	-	4,22	3,24	5,97	4,92	4,23	6,99	8,04	4,31	7,97	*	7,8
	Z089010a	3,88	-	-	-	4,5	6,49	6,91	6,5	5,88	6,08	4,56	7,8	*

Table 1. Barcode boat BC05, showing the results of the calculation of correlation between the dated tree-ring curves from the ship. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Samples x156, x240, x259 and x380 could not be dated. The two oak samples Z0890079 (x380) & Z0890119 (x156) cross-match with each other, producing a correlation value of $t = 6.78$ and the tree-ring curves from these two are averaged to the mean curve Z089M002. This mean curve could not be dated.

Filenames	-	-	Z089m001	
-	start	dates	AD 1399	
-	dates	end	AD 1581	
EP41592	AD	AD	12,13	Edinburgh Castle Norwegian data (Crone pers comm,)
stirling	AD	AD	11,49	Stirling Castle (Crone pers comm)
Z073m001	AD	AD	9,85	Barcode BC14 (Daly 2011c)
SM000012	AD	AD	8,86	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
8127M001	AD	AD	7,99	Ålborg Østerå + Boulevarden (Daly 2000a, 2001a)
ZEALAND0	AD	AD	7,52	Zealand (Daly unpubl,)
Z064M002	AD	AD	7,40	Sørenga 9 (Daly 2011a)
4077M00Z	AD	AD	7,39	Nyborg Slot Renaissance phase (Daly 2007)
Z040M001	AD	AD	7,29	Gåsehage Randers (Daly unpubl,)
Z0309M01	AD	AD	7,25	Barcode ship BC09 (Daly 2010d)
8111M001	AD	AD	7,19	Astrup K, (Daly 1998)
81M00004	AD	AD	7,13	kirker i Vendsyssel (Daly 1998)
4077M00X	AD	AD	7,00	Nyborg slot (Daly 1999)
00652M02	AD	AD	6,90	B&W vrug 2 (Daly 2000b)
SM100003	AD	AD	6,62	Ystad (Bartholin pers comm,)
2121M002	AD	AD	6,46	Suså Næstved (Daly 2001b)
midtjy17	AD	AD	6,34	Midtjylland (Christensen pers comm)
SM000005	AD	AD	6,15	Skaane+Blekinge (Bartholin pers comm,)
Z027M001	AD	AD	6,10	Amager Strand 6 planks (Daly 2008)
2136M001	AD	AD	5,99	Næstved, Det Gamle Rådhus (Daly 2000c)
Z043M001	AD	AD	5,66	FPL 77 4AM wreck (Daly 2009b)
0067M001	AD	AD	5,44	Copenhagen, Havnegade (Daly 1996)
Z0307M01	AD	AD	5,10	Barcode ship BC07 (Daly 2010c)
Z065M001	AD	AD	5,08	Bjørvika Kenneth Oslo (Daly 2011b)

Table 2. Barcode boat BC05, showing the results of the calculation of correlation between the average curve from the ship (table 1 above) and diverse site and master chronologies from Northern Europe. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Provenance

The dendrochronological analysis indicates (tables 2 and 3) that the ship was made from oaks that had grown in Southwest Sweden.

Analysis

For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the t-value ("t-test"), "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis, master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed. For calculation of the felling date for the trees used in the ship a sapwood statistic for Norway, developed by Christensen & Havemann (1998), is utilised. Here oaks have an average of 15 (-8 +6) sapwood rings.

Filenames	-	-	Z089014a	Z089004b	Z0890089	Z089012a	
-	start	dates	AD 1522	AD 1514	AD 1386	AD 1440	
-	dates	end	AD 1585	AD 1597	AD 1519	AD 1584	
4077M001	AD 1310	AD 1540	\	\	6,57	5,37	Nyborg slot (Daly 1999)
Z065M002	AD 1355	AD 1617	-	-	6,31	6,40	Bjørsvika Kenneth Oslo (Daly 2011b)
Z0309M01	AD 1395	AD 1561	-	4,89	-	6,77	Barcode ship BC09 (Daly 2010d)
Z0307M01	AD 1435	AD 1585	3,33	-	5,72	4,80	Barcode ship BC07 (Daly 2010c)
FTMAS2	AD 1318	AD 1572	3,02	-	5,34	-	Fenton Tower Scotland Norwegian data (Crone pers comm.)
Z0302M01	AD 1429	AD 1587	-	-	5,24	5,75	Barcode BC02 (Daly 2010b)
8127M001	AD 846	AD 1771	3,61	-	5,24	3,21	Ålborg østerå + boulevarden (Daly 2000a, 2001a)
2109m004	AD 1356	AD 1482	\	\	5,12	3,33	Smerup K. (Daly 1997)
Z040M001	AD 1386	AD 1567	-	3,57	4,93	4,04	Gåsehage Randers (Daly 2009a)
DUNTARVI	AD 1385	AD 1529	\	\	4,82	3,27	Duntarvi Norwegian data (Crone pers comm.)
Ep3mnall	AD 1361	AD 1539	\	\	4,78	3,88	Edinburgh Castle Norwegian data (Crone pers comm.)
8111M001	AD 1350	AD 1480	\	\	4,60	-	Astrup K. (Daly 1998)
SM000012	AD 1125	AD 1720	-	3,63	4,50	4,22	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
CARNCKx8	AD 1317	AD 1588	-	-	4,48	3,85	Carnock Scotland Norwegian data (Crone pers comm.)
SM000005	AD 1274	AD 1974	-	-	4,41	3,34	Skaane+Blekinge (Bartholin pers comm)
2121M002	AD 1052	AD 1596	-	3,59	4,41	-	Suså Næstved (Daly 2001b)
Z071m002	AD 1248	AD 1595	-	-	3,95	3,49	Barcode BC08 (Daly 2011c)
Z073m001	AD 1385	AD 1574	3,10	-	3,27	3,23	Barcode BC14 (Daly 2011c)
Z027M002	AD 1313	AD 1567	3,71	-	3,02	4,38	Amager Strand (Daly 2008)
Z0306M01	AD 1418	AD 1585	-	-	-	4,51	Barcode BC06 (Daly 2010a)
Z089m001	AD 1399	AD 1581	6,64	3,47	-	3,53	Barcode skib BC05 (Daly this report)

Table 3. Barcode boat BC05, showing the results of the calculation of correlation between four single tree-ring curves from the ship and diverse site and master chronologies from Northern Europe. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

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Catalogue

Catalogue format:

Filename
 Title and sample number
 Tree species (QUSP = *Quercus sp.*, oak, PISY = *Pinus sp.*, pine, FREX = *Fraxinus Excelsior*, ash) and number of years measured
 Chronological position of the tree-ring curve
 Number of sapwood years, presence of bark
 Felling date

Z072001a

NSM03010085 Barcode 05 x600 lot forud x549

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 165 years length

Dated AD 1416 to AD 1580

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 80.61 Sensitivity 0.16

Interpretation after AD 1588

68	105	105	78	58	63	49	55	64	52
55	65	60	65	57	56	53	56	61	50
43	47	53	46	39	51	57	71	54	50
53	57	41	45	30	35	37	30	30	32
36	37	38	48	35	40	34	35	35	40
31	34	46	42	42	63	65	45	82	82
107	97	120	176	136	102	181	169	125	103
148	180	90	65	58	80	67	83	94	97
131	99	106	96	86	153	89	106	117	135
106	136	144	142	143	166	174	145	132	137
123	102	95	89	65	70	77	71	71	88
89	88	90	53	60	63	69	63	52	53
56	64	70	71	80	91	90	93	118	100
83	71	64	59	65	68	82	99	106	124
126	114	137	135	132	109	109	134	184	98
64	52	56	76	61	83	73	68	69	68
58	57	56	53	36					

Z0890019

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x585 hudbord x501

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 84 years length

Dated AD 1482 to AD 1565

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 97.90 Sensitivity 0.18

Interpretation after AD 1573

183	127	127	110	96	133	115	83	79	93
95	120	104	108	129	127	77	69	80	94
86	89	126	149	97	167	149	148	155	169
153	141	133	122	144	100	119	73	64	112
134	98	87	92	124	117	85	50	48	58
73	63	58	107	78	83	73	78	97	102
105	112	97	90	75	55	42	42	55	78
63	83	76	65	77	65	74	74	84	94
82	102	109	75						

Z089002d

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x586 kjølbord x524

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 127 years length

Dated AD 1417 to AD 1543

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 161.24 Sensitivity 0.19

Interpretation after AD 1551

182	96	118	103	125	155	143	180	175	177
242	414	277	166	181	279	281	273	207	172
164	170	167	196	189	152	186	152	166	116
168	169	159	152	158	201	149	168	212	149
125	115	124	152	133	108	125	154	113	118
140	172	144	112	121	102	113	148	191	193
183	214	211	184	168	286	198	255	227	190
218	149	93	121	137	131	136	125	127	186
146	110	105	121	144	120	160	168	179	130
213	180	227	194	238	207	189	159	213	185
126	177	134	92	151	216	121	111	110	159
144	130	139	171	134	164	109	90	119	119
114	108	145	143	97	104	131			

Z089003a

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x587 hudbord x487

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 133 years length

Dated AD 1449 to AD 1581

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 163.52 Sensitivity 0.17

Interpretation after AD 1589

286	328	392	512	423	285	331	251	249	240
252	158	185	214	259	264	228	176	196	229
190	108	174	151	167	177	212	197	184	184
156	198	186	230	233	289	334	287	288	157
99	94	127	125	150	144	150	142	149	106
106	136	137	135	149	174	210	217	253	196
212	175	190	213	211	173	186	203	183	185
142	91	154	220	162	132	146	142	113	150
113	145	135	148	123	97	110	134	139	113
111	135	149	139	112	101	127	128	113	129
117	135	143	123	151	116	110	91	104	118
94	136	126	122	117	131	101	122	103	85
122	86	60	85	89	69	93	72	76	55
52	41	60							

Z089004b

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x588 hudbord x471

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 84 years length

Dated AD 1514 to AD 1597

2 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 239.35 Sensitivity 0.20

Interpretation AD 1602-16

161	214	224	199	198	199	135	189	201	135
185	140	155	104	121	126	176	194	149	109
104	112	178	254	259	250	215	215	225	206
180	220	145	90	176	152	196	312	223	233
218	261	278	174	248	301	352	334	515	659
541	411	364	374	380	470	265	470	354	305
308	374	277	298	233	261	179	239	283	265
238	256	335	262	248	239	232	176	156	132
111	120	147	203						

Z089005b

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x589 hudson x498

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 177 years length

Dated AD 1399 to AD 1575

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 120.34 Sensitivity 0.24

Interpretation after AD 1583

75	103	76	99	103	118	119	92	84	100
89	94	85	72	122	50	60	47	68	64
59	66	76	58	60	90	72	70	80	64
66	66	62	60	53	42	39	38	55	44
41	40	33	41	40	32	32	30	42	32
35	30	28	25	29	38	51	43	27	32
39	47	44	49	48	53	63	59	64	42
48	72	67	47	32	48	74	90	107	120
106	113	134	200	142	101	116	133	183	103
48	121	138	184	192	197	153	212	219	181
117	142	276	303	205	219	336	192	189	224
173	166	162	175	135	132	198	204	136	154
123	92	139	210	131	140	230	283	180	113
60	114	144	266	172	177	245	218	223	201
226	181	131	178	250	187	199	141	139	230
130	136	246	155	112	80	132	146	85	127
173	178	204	155	167	204	111	149	134	131
241	150	209	133	218	187	216			

Z089006b

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x591 hudson x467

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 147 years length

Dated AD 1432 to AD 1578

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 175.65 Sensitivity 0.18

Interpretation after AD 1586

101	265	293	150	254	190	182	188	283	254
205	236	227	364	201	268	303	275	198	190
178	204	196	134	139	145	206	204	214	176
258	265	223	182	145	176	268	271	181	208
157	243	232	274	346	176	205	173	119	138
242	165	166	152	172	211	107	87	91	119
111	107	115	111	147	143	114	102	131	209
140	161	187	224	167	216	181	203	215	196
182	195	164	181	185	132	155	120	98	136
197	122	122	134	138	123	105	111	110	139
123	111	108	171	145	136	154	155	172	182
168	193	192	220	167	123	165	122	158	204
190	181	168	161	184	163	170	172	184	202
186	197	179	139	166	161	141	175	149	146
143	150	154	159	150	149	128			

Z0890079

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x592 garneringsbord x380

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 135 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 99.43 Sensitivity 0.20

143	159	195	123	183	187	154	182	186	120
123	98	97	127	130	76	67	81	88	107
111	129	110	70	95	112	88	111	120	154
90	129	141	153	127	103	77	117	139	150
124	101	78	62	82	77	59	64	40	46
40	64	50	63	61	53	62	66	101	99
123	135	152	117	170	143	165	124	148	138
124	86	111	96	141	97	100	96	92	94
90	73	69	101	94	90	89	136	123	108
168	83	118	138	176	128	177	99	102	96
110	89	92	106	74	109	66	65	77	66
86	75	75	81	69	59	62	80	63	85
49	69	50	38	44	53	54	52	48	60
54	52	57	51	49					

Z0890089

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x593 hudbord x342

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 134 years length

Dated AD 1386 to AD 1519

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 113.71 Sensitivity 0.16

Interpretation after AD 1527

344	351	200	207	173	186	245	262	163	171
220	206	193	170	150	235	134	150	155	153
176	129	136	126	109	109	109	113	114	81
88	92	84	96	111	130	137	116	142	116
111	112	95	77	104	104	134	93	126	88
98	82	92	86	97	75	96	104	99	83
77	90	104	94	97	111	79	83	73	70
90	79	93	71	74	64	82	79	62	84
60	64	85	59	60	66	78	58	60	76
89	54	75	96	85	88	84	108	89	73
71	79	66	75	67	77	69	89	74	77
61	107	116	74	78	75	78	91	101	142
140	199	166	151	156	136	172	177	118	139
144	121	126	124						

Z089009a

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x594 hudson x475

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 138 years length

Dated AD 1414 to AD 1551

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 179.95 Sensitivity 0.25

Interpretation after AD 1559

110	64	41	54	109	51	52	46	38	46
32	35	41	80	75	100	49	86	73	66
85	69	44	37	42	67	65	49	55	105
95	106	119	190	171	135	91	93	111	119
111	52	50	57	147	204	239	266	323	287
209	217	151	110	82	100	100	109	92	66
215	290	355	231	251	267	272	251	274	297
277	300	197	303	260	151	135	160	165	255
249	177	298	274	236	205	198	305	261	248
308	365	263	345	344	351	391	418	448	391
252	373	328	263	308	227	132	215	274	167
162	237	309	233	144	134	126	138	148	137
94	144	195	195	189	150	276	195	259	299
228	277	179	249	169	111	129	139		

Z089010a

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x596 hudson x460

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 167 years length

Dated AD 1410 to AD 1576

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 110.85 Sensitivity 0.20

Interpretation after AD 1584

165	153	206	244	152	96	83	93	89	61
72	85	87	69	119	118	107	142	128	140
109	113	141	149	142	85	63	48	86	63
83	79	82	104	104	132	88	111	97	105
85	98	91	112	102	58	66	55	80	84
98	81	70	96	81	106	79	97	114	121
86	93	88	59	69	106	143	90	111	122
125	111	195	141	123	112	118	163	147	68
115	117	127	114	98	80	118	142	91	87
94	120	78	89	109	125	97	139	157	156
116	158	186	174	132	172	154	121	89	82
66	79	87	79	102	118	119	103	101	83
96	97	97	70	64	72	66	71	80	110
154	116	131	113	140	152	115	85	85	79
96	119	98	121	131	171	156	149	157	188
193	159	112	162	182	116	136	103	92	116
114	74	102	119	128	101	113			

Z0890119

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x597 garneringsbord x156

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 110 years length

Undated

13 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 74.74 Sensitivity 0.15

53	46	43	61	49	52	51	87	106	166
118	105	97	96	99	120	100	112	118	118
101	90	84	108	94	92	93	94	69	85
64	60	76	74	59	57	77	63	58	65
56	66	63	65	68	89	75	78	73	89
69	84	84	62	129	74	61	75	65	96
75	77	76	74	65	79	98	100	108	75
98	52	53	69	62	72	66	57	72	80
75	83	90	64	64	55	52	54	58	57
53	63	75	78	74	60	68	58	54	61
55	62	59	63	67	56	47	42	40	45

Z089012a

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x598 hudbord x503

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 145 years length

Dated AD 1440 to AD 1584

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 83.18 Sensitivity 0.21

Interpretation after AD 1592

70	95	66	81	45	58	71	120	100	103
125	173	120	122	95	81	101	83	78	86
76	77	103	85	76	103	60	59	100	68
79	78	83	71	90	67	67	40	57	54
65	58	48	71	66	65	57	91	53	60
74	65	50	81	82	72	85	76	60	48
54	56	74	55	67	86	70	144	102	97
60	119	174	153	191	139	185	180	251	131
92	99	128	104	110	120	114	113	85	85
122	80	69	49	45	31	37	30	44	44
43	47	54	56	73	58	72	59	59	65
70	89	89	77	58	66	72	60	68	85
91	83	62	66	97	88	104	87	77	93
90	100	73	54	74	78	96	94	87	91
50	75	65	90	94					

Z089013a

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x599 hudbord x447

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 86 years length

Dated AD 1485 to AD 1570

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 264.13 Sensitivity 0.26

Interpretation after AD 1578

413	460	460	245	151	135	186	270	343	298
213	412	324	236	175	253	304	316	317	395
465	314	433	418	478	441	502	458	377	260
386	337	257	408	268	156	305	398	257	258
279	386	322	227	253	179	243	295	205	132
225	203	252	210	135	257	228	218	289	178
211	153	201	228	125	121	188	144	181	160
147	205	142	190	136	258	256	227	307	262
224	194	152	154	192	159				

Z089014a

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x601 hudbord x450

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 64 years length

Dated AD 1522 to AD 1585

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 229.14 Sensitivity 0.17

Interpretation after AD 1593

358	279	296	347	300	257	215	229	231	198
293	246	132	219	240	249	217	214	271	220
304	330	295	289	172	220	301	203	170	228
203	215	197	183	268	228	202	220	322	277
250	280	278	220	196	190	169	248	211	184
191	222	235	205	264	250	174	112	118	141
167	172	169	181						

Z089101a

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x590 dekkbord x240

Raw Ring-width PCAB data of 81 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 128.54 Sensitivity 0.19

112	176	160	137	115	112	114	99	127	126
167	139	129	160	181	172	188	187	157	184
179	116	123	91	60	69	61	47	55	76
73	83	123	88	58	87	113	82	119	96
134	143	153	103	153	133	116	105	93	95
115	110	109	103	150	129	160	172	151	121
142	140	142	185	208	122	170	170	145	90
92	88	109	67	120	184	218	195	206	184
146									

Z089102a

NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x595 dekkbord x259

Raw Ring-width PISY data of 45 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 440.96 Sensitivity 0.24

154	168	343	492	485	510	553	558	521	631
520	595	359	148	459	523	548	566	574	492
515	589	740	568	448	450	394	414	428	527
431	552	275	378	472	604	477	317	199	307
242	269	281	508	259					

filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	group	extra start	extra end	interpretation / felling
	QUSP											
Z072001a	NSM03010085 Barcode 05 x600 lot forud x549	165	AD 1416	AD 1580	O	G	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1588
Z0890019	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x585 hudbord x501	84	AD 1482	AD 1565	T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1573
Z089002d	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x586 kjølbord x524	127	AD 1417	AD 1543	T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1551
Z089003a	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x587 hudbord x487	133	AD 1449	AD 1581	T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1589
Z089004b	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x588 hudbord x471	84	AD 1514	AD 1597	T	G	2	-	-	-	-	AD 1602-16
Z089005b	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x589 hudbord x498	177	AD 1399	AD 1575	T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1583
Z089006b	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x591 hudbord x467	147	AD 1432	AD 1578	T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1586
Z0890079	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x592 garneringsbord x380	135			T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	Undated
Z0890089	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x593 hudbord x342	134	AD 1386	AD 1519	T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1527
Z089009a	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x594 hudbord x475	138	AD 1414	AD 1551	T	C	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1559
Z089010a	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x596 hudbord x460	167	AD 1410	AD 1576	T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1584
Z0890119	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x597 garneringsbord x156	110			T	G	13	-	-	-	S1	Undated
Z089012a	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x598 hudbord x503	145	AD 1440	AD 1584	T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1592
Z089013a	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x599 hudbord x447	86	AD 1485	AD 1570	T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1578
Z089014a	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x601 hudbord x450	64	AD 1522	AD 1585	T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	after AD 1593
Z089101a	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x590 dekkbord x240 PCAB	81			T	G	-	-	-	-	H1	Undated
Z089102a	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 prøve x595 dekkbord x259 PISY	45			T	C	-	-	-	-	-	Undated
Z089m001	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 9 timber mean	183	AD 1399	AD 1581								
Z089m002	NMM03010085 Barcode skib 5 2 timber mean	161										Undated

Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion.
Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.